

Exploring the impact of LIV at Deep Underground Neutrino Experiment

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Abstract

Lorentz Invariance Violation (LIV) is a fundamental violation of space-time symmetry, implying that physical laws vary under Lorentz transformation. The neutrinos are weakly interacting fundamental particles which can act as a probe for understanding the violation of Lorentz invariance symmetry. Here, we consider intrinsic LIV effects that can exist even in a vacuum. We use an effective field theory known as Standard Model Extension (SME) as a framework to treat the LIV as a small perturbation to the standard matter Hamiltonian. The effective Hamiltonian can be implemented to investigate how the presence of LIV parameters modifies the neutrino oscillation probabilities. We particularly study the effect of CPT-violating LIV terms on mass-induced neutrino oscillations.

In this work, we explore the impact of LIV on neutrino oscillation probabilities in matter taking DUNE as a case study. We observe a significant effect on neutrino oscillations in the presence of a non-zero LIV parameter. We further investigate the impact of LIV parameters on the CP-measurement sensitivity at DUNE.

1 Introduction

Neutrinos are particles that interact weakly with matter. These particles can change their flavor as they travel. This is known as the phenomenon of neutrino oscillations. The detection of ν -oscillations itself implies a non-zero mass of ν 's which leads to physics beyond the Standard Model (BSM). This can be probed to explore non-standard (NS) physics effects which have the potential to affect the precise measurements of ν -oscillation parameters. Therefore, it becomes necessary to study the impact of these sub-dominant NS effects. Lorentz invariance violation (LIV) is one such NS physics scenario which can be probed via ν -oscillations. Lorentz invariance is the fundamental space-time symmetry which implies invariance under Lorentz transformation. The violation of Lorentz invariance arises from the breakdown of space-time symmetry. We consider LIV to be inherent in nature whose effects are also seen in a vacuum.

2 Formalism

The standard Hamiltonian of ν 's interacting with matter can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} H_{SI} &= H_{vacuum} + H_{matter} \\ &= \frac{1}{2E} U \begin{pmatrix} m_1^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & m_2^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & m_3^2 \end{pmatrix} U^\dagger + \sqrt{2} G_f N_e \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

The matter Hamiltonian (H_{matter}) arises due to the interaction of neutrinos with matter via CC and NC interactions. The vacuum Hamiltonian (H_{vacuum}) consists of the ν -mass matrix and the PMNS mixing matrix (U) [8]. The effects of LIV can be incorporated into ν -oscillations by considering the minimal Standard Model Extension (SME) framework [2]. In SME framework, the LIV effects can be treated as tiny perturbations to the standard ν -Hamiltonian. These effects are sub-dominant in nature and can be added to standard Hamiltonian as a matter potential. The effects of LIV on ν -oscillation probabilities can be described by a time-dependent perturbation theory as shown in [3, 4]. In presence of LIV, the effective Hamiltonian is [5],

$$\begin{aligned} H_{eff} &= H_{SI} + H_{LIV}, \\ H_{LIV} &= \left[\begin{pmatrix} a_{ee} & a_{e\mu} & a_{e\tau} \\ a_{e\mu}^* & a_{\mu\mu} & a_{\mu\tau} \\ a_{e\tau}^* & a_{\mu\tau}^* & a_{\tau\tau} \end{pmatrix} - \frac{4}{3} E \begin{pmatrix} c_{ee} & c_{e\mu} & c_{e\tau} \\ c_{e\mu}^* & c_{\mu\mu} & c_{\mu\tau} \\ c_{e\tau}^* & c_{\mu\tau}^* & c_{\tau\tau} \end{pmatrix} \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The additional matter potential like term H_{LIV} is the contribution from CPT-violating ($a_{\alpha\beta}$) and CPT-conserving LIV ($c_{\alpha\beta}$). These LIV parameters quantify the impact of Lorentz invariance violation on probabilities. We consider the Sun-centered celestial equatorial frame as the reference frame as it is roughly inertial [7, 1]. In this work, we have only taken the CPT-violating LIV parameters $a_{\alpha\beta} = |a_{\alpha\beta}| e^{i\phi_{\alpha\beta}}$. The impact of $a_{\alpha\beta}$ on the ν -oscillation probabilities at DUNE is studied along with its impact on the CP-measurement sensitivities [9].

3 Methodology

We use the GLoBES framework [6] to simulate the DUNE experiment. The effects of LIV can be studied by incorporating the effective Hamiltonian (H_{eff}) in this framework. We have fixed the values of oscillation parameters at $\theta_{12}=34.51^\circ$, $\theta_{13} = 8.44^\circ$, $\theta_{23} = 47^\circ$, $\Delta m_{21}^2 [10^{-5} eV^2] = 7.56$, $\Delta m_{31}^2 [10^{-3} eV^2] = 2.55$, $\delta_{CP} = -\pi/2$ and taking normal hierarchy as the true hierarchy. We can then obtain the numerically calculated oscillation probabilities. We can also define a statistical χ^2 in the framework to quantify the impact of LIV on the physics sensitivities of DUNE. We define the statistical χ^2 as show below where $N_{true}^{i,j}$ and $N_{test}^{i,j}$ are the true and test events.,

$$\chi^2 \equiv \min_{\eta} \sum_i \sum_j \frac{[N_{true}^{i,j} - N_{test}^{i,j}]^2}{N_{true}^{i,j}} \quad (3)$$

Figure 1: Plot of appearance probability $P_{\mu e}$ (top) for a_{ee} (left), $a_{e\mu}$ (middle) and $a_{e\tau}$ (right) and $P_{\mu\mu}$ (bottom) for $a_{\mu\mu}$ (left), $a_{\mu\tau}$ (middle) and $a_{\tau\tau}$ (right).

4 Results

In figure 1, we have explored the impact of LIV parameters $a_{\alpha\beta}$ on the ν -oscillation probabilities at DUNE. The black line represents the no LIV case whereas the blue (green) line signifies the case of positive (negative) LIV parameters. We have varied the neutrino energy in 0.5-10 GeV. We observe that the probability channel $P_{\mu e}$ is most affected in the presence of $a_{e\mu}$ & $a_{e\tau}$, whereas the impact due to a_{ee} is nominal. For positive(negative) a_{ee} & $a_{e\mu}$, we see an increase(decrease) in the probability values. However, we observe an opposite nature for $a_{e\tau}$.

In figure 2, we have studied the impact of $a_{\alpha\beta}$ with their corresponding phases on the CP-violation and CP-precision sensitivities at DUNE. We consider the off-diagonal elements $a_{e\mu}$, $a_{e\tau}$ and $a_{\mu\tau}$ considering only one LIV parameters at a time. The black line represents the no LIV case, whereas the red line represents the $a_{\alpha\beta} = 0.5$ case & the shaded band signifies the variation of $\phi_{\alpha\beta} \in [-\pi, \pi]$. In the top panels, we have explored the CP-violation sensitivities at DUNE. We have varied the δ_{CP} phase in $\in [-\pi, \pi]$. We see that the CPV sensitivity is mostly enhanced although, the presence of $\phi_{\alpha\beta}$ can significantly alter the sensitivities. For $a_{\mu\tau}$, the sensitivity deteriorates for the complete δ_{CP} space. The presence of $\phi_{\alpha\beta}$ can introduce degeneracy in the δ_{CP} measurement. The CP-precision sensitivities are shown in the bottom panels. The true value of δ_{CP} is fixed at $-\pi/2$. We see $\phi_{e\mu}$ dependent enhancement/suppression in the sensitivities in the presence of $a_{e\mu}$. In the case of $a_{e\tau}$ and $a_{\mu\tau}$, the presence of the LIV phase is seen to enhance the sensitivities.

5 Summary and Conclusion

The presence of NS physics effects such as LIV can significantly impact the CP-measurement sensitivities. We see that LIV parameters can alter the neutrino oscillation probabilities. The presence of LIV phase can bring degeneracy in δ_{CP} measurement at DUNE.

Figure 2: CPV and CP-Precision sensitivities at DUNE for $a_{e\mu}$ (left), $a_{e\tau}$ (middle) and $a_{\mu\tau}$ (right).

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